

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14229865>

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF “BRAND JOURNALISM”

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Annotation. Brand journalism has evolved significantly over the past decades, becoming a key strategy for companies to build deeper relationships with their audiences and strengthen brand identity. This article explores the history and trends shaping brand journalism, starting from its roots in corporate communications to its integration with modern digital tools and social media. It examines how the rise of content marketing and the shift toward interactive, engaging storytelling have transformed the marketing landscape. Additionally, the article highlights the growing importance of authenticity, transparency, and emotional connection in the way brands communicate with consumers today. The integration of advanced technologies, such as AI and big data, is also discussed as a significant factor in the personalized approach that modern brand journalism now takes.

Keywords: Brand journalism, Content marketing, Interactive storytelling, Digital media, Corporate communications, Social media, Consumer engagement, AI, Big data, Brand identity.

Аннотация. Бренд-журналистика значительно эволюционировала за последние десятилетия, став важной стратегией для компаний, направленной на установление более глубоких отношений с аудиторией и укрепление идентичности бренда. В этой статье рассматриваются история и тенденции, формирующие бренд-журналистику, начиная от ее истоков в корпоративных коммуникациях и до интеграции с современными цифровыми инструментами и социальными сетями. Анализируется, как рост контент-маркетинга и переход к интерактивному, вовлекающему повествованию изменили маркетинговый ландшафт. Также рассматривается растущая важность аутентичности, прозрачности и эмоциональной связи в общении брендов с потребителями сегодня. Обсуждается влияние новых технологий, таких как искусственный интеллект и большие данные, как значимый фактор в персонализированном подходе, который бренд-журналистика применяет в наши дни.

Ключевые слова: Бренд-журналистика, Контент-маркетинг, Интерактивное повествование, Цифровые медиа, Корпоративные коммуникации, Социальные сети, Взаимодействие с потребителями, Искусственный интеллект, Большие данные, Идентичность бренда.

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of “**brand journalism**” as a distinct concept in the world of media and marketing is a significant shift in how companies communicate with their audiences. Traditionally, brands relied heavily on advertising to reach their customers, but over the past two decades, as media landscapes evolved and consumer behaviors changed, companies began to create journalistic-style content that serves both their marketing objectives and their desire to build trust and engage with consumers. This transition can be traced through various phases in history, especially through the development of content marketing, the rise of digital platforms, and the ongoing evolution of media strategies.

Before the term “**brand journalism**” came into common usage, the idea of corporations using media to communicate with their audiences was already in practice. Companies had long recognized the importance of shaping their image and influencing public opinion through communications strategies. This began in earnest in the early 20th century, particularly in the form of corporate magazines and internal publications.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

One of the first examples of what we can consider the precursor to brand journalism was **John Deere’s “The Furrow,”** which began publishing in 1900. This publication provided valuable farming-related content and advice to its readers, while subtly promoting John Deere's products. Though it wasn't “journalism” in the traditional sense, it marked a shift in corporate communications towards storytelling and information-sharing rather than direct selling. According to **Haughey (2003)**, this type of content was an early attempt to forge an ongoing relationship between the company and its audience through informative content rather than blatant advertisements. “In the early 20th century, companies began using storytelling to promote their products and build customer loyalty. This would evolve into what we now call 'brand journalism’”[**Haughey, 2003**].

In the late 20th century, the advertising industry began to see challenges to its traditional model, particularly with the rise of consumer resistance to interruptive advertising. As audiences began to tune out conventional ads, marketers sought new ways to engage them. **Content marketing** emerged as a way to fill this gap, by creating valuable, relevant content to engage consumers and build long-term relationships.

In 2001, **Joe Pulizzi** coined the term “**content marketing**”, emphasizing that brands could create useful content that would naturally attract and engage their target audiences, rather than forcefully pushing products through traditional ads. With this shift, brands began to adopt journalistic principles—producing articles, videos, and other forms of media that told compelling stories and provided real value, all while aligning with the brand’s messaging. This development laid the foundation for what

would later be called **brand journalism**. “Content marketing and brand journalism go hand-in-hand: both aim to inform, engage, and build trust with an audience, without the overt 'sell' of traditional advertising” [Pulizzi, 2014]. As Pulizzi (2014) notes, the core objective of content marketing is not to sell directly but to **educate, inform, and entertain**. By focusing on storytelling rather than mere promotion, brands could offer a more engaging experience for consumers. **Brand journalism** is thus a subset of content marketing, one that specifically uses journalistic techniques to tell the brand’s story in a way that mimics traditional journalism. This shift meant that the lines between advertising and journalism began to blur.

The explosion of the internet, particularly social media platforms like **Facebook**, **Twitter**, **Instagram**, and later **YouTube**, gave brands the direct ability to communicate with their audiences without the need for traditional media outlets. This new reality fundamentally changed the dynamics of brand communication, offering companies an unprecedented opportunity to tell their stories on their own terms. The rise of social media platforms not only allowed for one-to-one communication between brands and consumers but also provided brands with the opportunity to interact with their audience in real-time. As noted by **Chris Brogan** and **Julien Smith** in *The Impact Equation* (2012), social media provided a platform for **interactive storytelling**. Brands could now create content that invited audience participation and allowed for continuous dialogue, shifting the focus from traditional, static advertising to dynamic and participatory communication. “Social media has transformed brand journalism by making brands not just sellers of products, but also creators of valuable, engaging content” [Brogan & Smith, 2012]. The **interactivity** afforded by digital platforms is a key feature of brand journalism today. Brands began publishing blog posts, articles, videos, and other content that resembled the style of traditional journalism, but with a focus on their products, services, or values. These narratives allowed for more emotional engagement with the audience. In turn, it encouraged **audience interaction** via comments, shares, and likes, making the communication much more dynamic and reciprocal.

RESULTS

As digital platforms became more ingrained in consumer daily life, brand journalism evolved from a marketing tactic into an integral part of many companies’ overall **corporate strategy**. It is no longer just about promoting a product or service, but about building a strong, authentic brand identity that resonates with consumers on an emotional level. Today’s consumers expect more from brands than just advertisements—they want transparency, authenticity, and a connection to the company’s values. **David Edelman (2010)** discusses how consumers now view brands as **storytellers** rather than just companies pushing products. He argues that for brands

to be successful, they must engage in meaningful conversations with their audience, telling stories that align with their values, rather than relying solely on traditional advertising strategies. “Brands today need to act as storytellers, not just marketers. Brand journalism allows brands to do this by offering content that connects with consumers' emotions and values” [Edelman, 2010]. As Edelman (2010) highlights, **brand journalism** has become a key tool for companies to build an **emotional connection** with their audience. By creating content that reflects their core values and tells authentic stories, companies can generate consumer loyalty, trust, and long-term engagement. This type of content does not just inform—it shapes how consumers perceive the brand and its identity. As the media landscape continues to evolve, brand journalism is becoming even more integrated with **interactive technology**, **data-driven insights**, and **personalized content**. Brands are now leveraging AI, big data, and machine learning to create highly personalized content that speaks directly to individual consumers based on their behaviors, preferences, and interactions. Moreover, **brand journalism** is no longer confined to just written articles and videos. It now extends to podcasts, virtual events, and interactive online experiences. The demand for real-time, highly relevant, and visually engaging content has led to the rise of formats like **live-streaming** and **short-form video content**, where brands can engage with their audience in more spontaneous and direct ways.

CONCLUSION

The evolution of brand journalism has mirrored the rapid changes in the media landscape, driven by technological advancements, the rise of digital platforms, and shifting consumer behaviors. What began as a tactic for improving corporate communications has now become a sophisticated, strategic tool that enables brands to tell their stories in compelling, authentic, and engaging ways. By embracing journalistic principles, brands can connect with their audience on a deeper level, build trust, and establish long-term relationships. As **Edelman (2010)** and **Pulizzi (2014)** suggest, brand journalism is not just a marketing strategy; it is an essential element of modern brand communication. As we move forward, the integration of data, interactive technologies, and evolving storytelling formats will continue to shape the future of brand journalism, making it an indispensable tool for brands in a highly competitive and media-saturated world.

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